

Fashion Design: Desires and Emotions

When Fashion Students Respond to Design for Emotion

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Abstract

Clothing through its proximity to the body and its ability to impact the wearer's emotional state suggests that as a discipline fashion design relies heavily on the principles of design for emotion. However, in discussions on design methodology, fashion is rarely given much attention as a field where desire and emotion play a central role in the design process.

The aim of this paper is to provide a fashion perspective on design for emotion. My primary focus will be on the way fashion design students respond to the inclusion of 'emotion' as a design criteria; and common themes that arise through such design will be discussed. While it is obvious they respond to this on a subconscious level in almost all their design work; something interesting happens when this is heightened to a conscious usage of emotion centered design tools, enquiry and methodology. The resulting outcomes are not only focused on consumers' emotional needs, but also become imbued with that of the designers' realities, dreams and desires.

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Introduction

“ The art of dress is difficult to define, but we regard it as the relationship of body and dress recognized by members of a cultural group who use an aesthetic code to express who they are. The result gives the dressed person emotional satisfaction and has the potential to provide pleasure to both wearer and observer. ” (Eicher, Evenson, Lutz, 2000, pp.293)

The emotive impact of clothing is a universal experience, one that is heightened through the relationship clothes have with the body they adorn or adhere to. It is not uncommon to hear accounts of how certain garments impact the wearer’s physical and emotional state simply through color, fit, style or surface pattern. The need *and* desire to be clothed ensures the universality of the ‘language of clothing’ (Lurie, 1981, Calefato, 2004, Lauwaert, 2006 etc.) and aesthetic codes that may be culturally specific and different, yet commonly experienced in a variety of ways. The multiple theories on the origins of dress allude to the fact that clothing can simultaneously fulfill a number of requirements of and for the human body. While some regard the primary function of clothing to be protection, as we examine the numerous ways and contexts in which clothes are worn, we begin to realize that there are less pragmatic reasons and desires at play behind the human urge to dress the body.

As a discipline of design, fashion is deeply centered on tapping the real and imagined powers of clothing as part of the design process and in this paper I highlight the role targeting human emotions can play in design for fashion. My focus will be on the way fashion design students respond to the inclusion of ‘emotion’ as a design criteria within a studio brief. In doing so I will discuss the common methods, themes and outcomes that arise through such design. Examples of student work will be used to illustrate these common themes that are eventually seen as being closely linked to the students’ dreams and desires.

Clothing, Emotion and the Body

Clothing has been likened to a form of language (Lurie, 1981, Lauwaert, 2006, etc.) making it a visual articulation of the body, whereby it becomes a tool for communicating (and reading) the intentions of the wearer. This communicative ability of clothing, though

often culturally specific, can be further manipulated to impact both the wearer and the observer. In this way it allows you to *clearly* state something about yourself. Playing with visual elements and semiotic signs and symbols (aesthetic codes) in dress, various combinations can be derived through which the material structure of clothing can be determined. The global nature of the fashion system means that more culturally specific meanings and symbols vested in items of dress through the process of globalization become universally understood and applied to everyday clothing. By being exposed to this global system of dress and fashion as well as to the everyday experience of clothing fashion students gain their design language and philosophy, which I will discuss later in this paper.

Dressing the body is a sensory experience and goes far beyond a physical activity by responding to “cultural codes that allow human beings to [experience,] express and interpret visual and other sensual information about [themselves and other] individuals” (Eicher, Evenson, Lutz, 2000, pp.292). Our first and foremost interaction with our clothes comes through touch and the sensation of fabric and textures on the body. However, with this intimate, second-skin like experience come numerous other responses, such as the aesthetic responses to form, shape, color and texture that have the ability to delight, please or in some circumstances even displease the wearer. We are also influenced by the way the fabric and the garment facilitate (or in some cases impede) movement, gestures and posture. Beyond that we begin to associate shapes and symbols with collective experiences and socially prescribed meanings (non-material attributes). These come to be determined through social interaction whereby we attach meaning and *mana* (Lurie, 1981, pp.30) to physical characteristics i.e. certain shapes, patterns and forms of dress, which continue to evolve and change over time. Thus the ability of clothing to influence the wearer’s physical and emotive state is enhanced by the “charged” nature of such objects, that Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton define as having the psychic energy of others invested in them (Csikszentmihalyi, Rochberg-Halton, 1981, pp.8). This vested energy from numerous agents also includes that of the designer or originator of the clothing.

Fashion Design

For this paper it is important to state the difference between the terms ‘clothing’ and ‘fashion’. My use of the term clothing refers to Eicher’s definition of dress as the “the assemblage of body modifications and body supplements displayed by a person and worn

at a particular moment in time” (Eicher, Evenson, Lutz, 2000, pp.4). These can be items or garments that are either attached to or worn on the body. However the term fashion, though commonly used in reference to a person’s clothes, has broader implications as ‘a system of change’ that relies on the spirit of the times to determine its shape and direction. As a term and as a larger concept fashion is not only applicable to clothing but also to other material and non-material items such as food, furniture, language, taste etc. While this paper focuses on the design process of students studying fashion, it is important to note that in reality they deal more so with the design of clothing or dress, which is ultimately for the fashion system.

Current texts on the design process for fashion, usually targeted at the student body, are often simplistic in their discussion on the design process for this field. Design for fashion is mainly described as being concerned with the visceral elements and some behavioral properties of products. The process of design begins with some sort of thematic or inspiration sourcing, which is heavily informed and influenced by seasonal trend information available on color, fabric, styling etc. The development of design ideas rely on the linking of these trends to a theme, which also includes the consideration of historic styles of clothing (fashion looks to the past to predict the future) that may be relevant to the chosen theme. Often the theme itself is derived from a particular style of historic clothing (for eg. Victorian, Edwardian, 1920s etc), which helps determine the design. Following or concurrent to this process is the sourcing of materials and trims that also further inform and inspire the design. These are then finalized into finished designs that are sampled and fine tuned for further production. While this is clearly an over simplification on my part in attempt to condense these texts, the lack of focus on the reflective aspect of design is very apparent to anyone who may be interested in a more critical or analytical discussion on the design process. All texts stress on the need to focus on a target market or consumer group, its tastes, needs and aspirations; however, with the exclusion of some types of performance clothing (outwear, sportswear etc), little or no importance is given to the impact the design may have on the wearer and what role this impact may play on the actual design and outcome.

The complexities of the fashion system and its reliance on time and change combined with the ephemeral nature of the fashion product can tend to limit in-depth and reflective practices when it comes to design. However in a broader context this system of design does target one key emotional response from the wearer – and that is the awareness of

being 'in fashion'. Some would argue that in comparison to other taste based experiential responses wearers may have from clothes, the consciousness of being in fashion is perhaps the most satisfying. Another important aspect within the practice of fashion design is the role of the designer as the 'creator' and 'originator' of style. Kawamura (2005) highlights the celebrity status and importance of the designer and designer's philosophy that is directly linked to the product in the field of fashion. This status is often the driving factor behind the purchase and consumer enjoyment of the product. Both these characteristics of the fashion product add to emotive influence of fashioned clothing that go beyond the visceral and behavioral level to being a more reflective level of user response¹. Furthermore, for many designers practicing in the field of fashion the aim is to provide customers with unique, pleasurable or personal experiences through clothing, making the design of clothing highly suited to a discussion on design and emotion.

Clothing and Emotion – Assignment for Fashion Design Students

It was in response to the aforementioned aspects of clothing and design of clothing, which already had the ability to influence wearer emotions, that made me consider the inclusion of 'emotion' as a design criteria for fashion design students. The diverse and often poetic nature of academic writing on clothing combined with the lack of discussion on a more reflective process in design for such clothing was another driving factor behind this. The aim was to offer students a different focus or design process; one where the consumer or wearer response was key to the design outcome and to encourage them to explore other avenues of research and perhaps even test their own emotive response to clothing as part of this research.

The 'fashion and emotion' assignment brief was given to students as their final project as part of a fashion design studio course (Spring semester, 2008). The students taking the course were mainly Juniors (3rd year) or Sophomores (2nd year), studying fashion at Columbia College Chicago, USA. A previous version of this brief was given to Junior level students studying fashion at Massey University, New Zealand (Fall semester, 2007). The brief highlighted the ability of clothing to impact the wearer's emotions and experiences and required students to enhance some aspect of this in their design. They were required to focus on a core emotion or function that they wished to design for and

¹ See Norman (2004) for the three levels of the cognitive and emotional systems for design of products – visceral, behavioral and reflective

then develop ideas, research and designs solutions. Students were not limited to exploring positive user responses and could also focus on negative user experiences or emotions that a wearer may have in clothing. Through the 'fashion and emotion' brief I was hoping to encourage a shift from the purely thematic-trend based model of fashion design, which did not always allow for questioning or reflective design ideation. Unfortunately this also meant that students would be going against the grain of common industry practice in fashion, but this was considered an acceptable risk in the hope of achieving diverse and perhaps even better design processes and outcomes.

As part of their design process students already tend to consider their relationship with clothing on a sub-conscious level. In a separate informal survey freshman level design students expressed their opinion on fashion and clothing as being a form of self-expression and through this having the ability to transform and impact the wearer in numerous ways. Students stressed on the 'feel good' factor that clothes could lend and also how they could negatively impact the wearer as well, which highlighted the fact that an awareness of the emotive quality of clothing already existed within the student psyche. However a focused and conscious application of this would perhaps allow them to make better use of this intrinsic ability of clothing, which could also lead to stronger design.

Student Response to Design for Emotion

Despite the external focus and outcomes of design it remains a deeply personal activity as the designer's dreams and desires become inseparable from the ideas and product. And as I mentioned earlier the imbuing of the designer's identity and tastes into the design is very suited to the fashion system. Through the design process it is natural for the designer's aesthetic tastes and experiences to be projected onto the designed object. This became very obvious in the way students responded to the brief, where more often than not their starting point was reflection on their own tastes and ideals, as well as their identity, stage in life and relationship with dress.

As this was not meant to be a quantitative research project, in presenting the outcomes of the student work I would like to focus on some common themes that arose as well as common approaches and working methods. Beyond the sourcing of stimuli and borrowing of aesthetic codes from their surrounding influences, majority of the students explored the positive and empowering nature of clothing - a reflection of their own

admiration of the craft and design of clothing. This included notions of ‘power’, ‘protection’, ‘comfort’ and ‘euphoria’ experienced through the wearing and performance of certain types of dress. These were in direct alignment with the theories of clothing I discussed earlier and alluded to the functional *and* magical aspects of dress. Role-play and understanding the relationship of the body and dress are also were some common methods that the students incorporated in their work.

The understanding and informed reference to the semiotics of dress was also a key factor in the students’ design, where they relied on the historic or culturally specific signs and symbols trapped in clothing styles to communicate their ideas. This was particularly useful as often they were designing items of clothing that they had never personally worn (such as a formal suit) or needed to wear.

Semiotics of Dress

The semiotics of dress play a crucial role as part of the fashion students’ design communication and vocabulary. It’s often through manipulation of the visual aesthetics and symbolic markers that intangible emotions can be made tangible in dress.

Understanding the impact that material and non-material attributes of clothing have had on people (individual and collective) in the past allows for a tried and tested resource of emotive stimuli that can be applied to design. This is a useful tool in creating a bond with the wearer, as a result of the common understanding of the aesthetic codes present in the designed garment.

While exploring notion of ‘power’ experienced through clothes, the obvious challenge for students was whether a natural outcome of wearing clothing could be further enhanced to achieve such an effect. Reference to past styles and clothing that had prior record of such wearer response was how most students began their design exploration. In doing this, one student studied the way fashion magazines tend to portray the three-piece suit as an empowering garment for men and women and made the link between this intangible emotion and clothing (Fig 1). She also looked at the basic elements that made up the suit and how function and symbolism could co-exist in one garment, or that symbolism could *shape* and *determine* function. The shoulder pads, lapels, collars, cuffs, gender specific textiles and detailing etc were all seen as visual markers of [masculine] power and used strategically to design clothes that could heighten the wearer’s experience of power.

Tightness and structure were also seen to have a similar user response and were considered to create these designs.

Fig 1: 'Power' (Karol Borrero, BFA Fashion Design, 2008, Columbia College Chicago)

Following a similar concept, another student explored visual cues of power in clothing commonly associated with royalty or those in positions of power. She made reference to the costume styles of Elizabeth I (Fig 2), again making use of the vested symbolism in dress from a point in time when clothing reflected power and status as opposed to the individual identity of the wearer. Embellishments, corsetry and exaggerated size, structure and fit of 17th century European women's costume were examined for their symbolic status and subsequently incorporated in the design due to their emotive abilities. Other symbolic cues explored by students included the use of decoration and detailing that would generate the wearer's response either by appearing familiar or nostalgic (Fig 6, pg. 11); and also involved the use of color or motifs that may appear culturally specific or related to rites and rituals. Various elements of dress that have strong stereotypes attached to them, such as the color pink, naïve detailing etc. were all used consciously in order to make full use of their symbolic value.

Fig 2: 'Power' (Maureen Sullivan, BFA Fashion Design, 2008, Columbia College Chicago)

The Body and Clothing

The physical relationship of the body with clothes and the material structure of clothing was an important aspect of the students' work. In comparison to prior design projects, this was the first time these students were required to interact with the emotions and sensations of the human body dressed *in* clothing in order to design clothing. The textural qualities of textiles, seams of garments, fit, sizing, shape etc. all played an important role, as students attempted to provide the body with multiple tactile experiences. And by far this had the most interesting outcome as students considered in their work the protective, comforting, liberating, secretive and even restrictive power of clothes. In this the body became a primary subject for the design process and was the site for multiple explorations.

Again in exploring the 'power' of dress, the corset was explored as a pleasurable and powerful garment rather than the restrictive garment it is usually viewed as. Volume was used as a tool to increase body mass in certain areas, again a way of increasing the body's

presence and dominance through clothing. In this way body dominant² and body subordinate³ dress were used in unison to create ‘powerful’ clothing. Another common theme here was the need to offer protection to the body, which included not only physical protection but also psychological comfort. Equating clothing to architecture for the body one student considered structures and shapes that were derived from an architectural viewpoint that were ‘softened’ and molded to fit and protect the wearer (Fig 3).

Fig 3: ‘Protection’ (Karen Hernandez, BFA Fashion Design, 2008, Columbia College Chicago)

Interaction with soft, bulky, enveloping structures like that of bed linens and quilts, for example, was also seen as an experiential method of coming to terms with designing a soft protective garment shell (Fig 4 & 5). While these explorations may appear whimsical the outcomes were not too dissimilar to down-filled winter jackets and other such protective outer-wear garments. The physical presence of clothing on the body was expanded upon by some who saw the potential of clothes as close companions that could

² Body dominant dress is one “that merges the body and dress, with the dress emphasizing the shape of the body” (Eicher, Evenson, Lutz, 2000, pp.323).

³ “Body subordinate is the “form of dress that may diverge from the form of the body, essentially covering the body and becoming an independent form with the body subordinate to the dress placed on it” (ibid, pp.323).

comfort or protect the wearer through the combination of material and non-material attributes.

Fig 4 & 5: 'Comfort' (Kerryn Trollope, BDes Fashion Design, 2007, Massey University, New Zealand)

Fig 6: 'Comfort / Protected' (Jacinta Wong, BFA Fashion Design, 2008, Columbia College Chicago)

Soft structures combined with 'cute' design were also considered to give the wearer a sense of familiarity and warmth (Fig 6). The need for the body to be physically and emotionally self-sufficient was another common concern for students, who felt that

contemporary culture and its digital tools encouraged individuals to remain isolated as opposed to being reliant on others. The ipod, iphone etc. were also seen as markers of this isolation, and this notion was expanded upon to create clothing that could perhaps act as a microhabitat for the wearer. As a flip side of this some students also explored how clothing could help individuals re-connect again by making use of visual and physical connecting devices such as continuous prints, magnets etc. to aid social interaction. The students' enhanced awareness of physical and emotional connects with clothing were positive outcomes of this design process.

Negative or restrictive aspects of clothing were also popular themes in student work. The shared experiences of being in clothing that was either too tight, too big, too bright etc. helped students explore ways of making an individual even more uncomfortable or awkward through their clothes. While these outcomes were not necessarily designs that could be considered marketable or wearable they did help build an understanding of what bad design could do to even the simplest of products, as well as the possibility of such design becoming acceptable through the fashion system.

Role-Play

“Clothing creates the possibility of retreating inside yourself, and from there outwards, to be yourself – to be me” (Lauwaert, 2006, pp.173)

As discussed earlier, clothing has the ability to enhance the wearer's experience of their body, both physically and emotionally, making it a transformative object. However this experience also relies on interaction with other clothed bodies and the performance of clothing – making clothing a performative object as well. Notions of role-play and fantasy are not far removed from this aspect of dress and these were common methods for design exploration amongst the students as they came to realize the transformative and performative powers of dress; often through putting themselves in performative situations. Experiencing first hand what it felt like to wear a certain fabric or style of clothing allowed students to respond through design more effectively. In the words of one student who explored aspects of familiarity and comfort in clothing by dressing like a 'hobo', “it was much easier to do things like a hobo when dressed like one.” Designing clothes that resembled the hobo aesthetic (one not too different from pre-loved or

deconstructed jeans or layered styles) meant that she could offer a wearer the comfort of being themselves and being inconspicuous.

Conclusion

While the students' projects were often specific to their immediate surroundings and stimuli, the outcomes of this brief were relatively similar when one compares the students' work from Chicago and New Zealand. Both sets of students responded with themes and ideas that were intrinsically linked to their own lifestyles, aesthetic tastes as well as their social beliefs and insecurities. As the students had a limited time frame for the project (5-6weeks) and were mainly required to submit design in the form of 2D explorations, the limitations of the exercise were the lack of deeper experimentation and testing of the design ideas, materials and models. More time spent on 3D explorations by making the designs into tangible products would have allowed for further reflection on the way bodies and wearers would respond, both in terms of material make-up and to the symbolic aspects used in the designs. However the *conscious* application of the semiotics of dress, as well as the beginnings of experimenting with the relationship clothes have with the body as part of the design process were both exciting outcomes for the students. The reflection on wearer response allowed them to develop a different viewpoint and angle of approaching design, which I believe resulted in deeper design enquiry on the part of the fashion students.

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